

1 **Zbtb12 activates receptors of the FNDC family with functions in tolerance and self non-self**
2 **discrimination, as well as a limited set of genes with TRA function.**

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7 We studied total transcription in cells with engineered over-expression of Zbtb12 in HEK293 coupled with
8 RNA-sequencing. Zbtb12 could independently transactivate TRA expression. Zbtb12 ectopic expression
9 could induce expression of mucins which function as a family in thymic self instruction for negative
10 selection during lymphocyte development in the mTEC.

11 Citations

12 1. Han, D., Liu, G., Oh, Y., Oh, S., Yang, S., Mandjikian, L., Rani, N., Almeida, M.C., Kosik, K.S. and
13 Jang, J., 2023. ZBTB12 is a molecular barrier to dedifferentiation in human pluripotent stem cells. Nature
14 communications, 14(1), p.632.

15 2. Keightley, M.C., Carradice, D.P., Layton, J.E., Pase, L., Bertrand, J.Y., Wittig, J.G., Dakic, A.,
16 Badrock, A.P., Cole, N.J., Traver, D. and Nutt, S.L., 2017. The Pu. 1 target gene Zbtb11 regulates
17 neutrophil development through its integrase-like HHCC zinc finger. Nature communications, 8(1),
18 p.14911.